

Some Square Planar Complexes of Platinum(II) with 2,5-Dihydroxyacetophenone and N-4-Methylphenylglyoxal Schiff Bases

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Tridentate Schiff bases, *N*-2,5-dihydroxyacetophenacylideneanthranilic acid (H_3 DAPA), *N*-2,5-dihydroxyacetophenacylidene-2,5-dichloroaniline (H_2 DAP DA), *N*-4-methylphenacylideneanthranilic acid (HMPAA) and *N*-4-methylphenacylidene-*o*-aminophenol (HMPAP) react with Pt^{II} to give complexes of composition, (a) H^+ $[Pt(C_{15}H_{11}NO_4)Cl]^-$ (1), $[Pt(C_{14}H_{10}NO_2Cl_2)Cl]$ (2), $[Pt(C_{16}H_{12}NO_3)Cl]$ (3), and $[Pt(C_{16}H_{12}NO_2)Cl]$ (4). The complexes are characterised as four-coordinate square planar on the basis of analysis, molar conductance, magnetic, electronic, infrared and pmr spectral studies. All these complexes behave as non-electrolytes with the exception of 1 which is shown to be uni-unielectrolytic nature.

SOME square planar complexes of C_{4v} symmetry have been discussed in recent years¹⁻⁵. We report in this communication the magnetic and spectral properties of typical square planar complexes of new tridentate Schiff bases, H_3 DAPA, H_2 DAPDA, HMPAA and HMPAP with Pt^{II} . The three orbital parameters Δ_1 , Δ_2 and Δ_3 describe the ligand field splitting in such complexes.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. The ligands (tridentate Schiff bases, *N*-2,5-dihydroxyacetophenacylideneanthranilic acid, *N*-2,5-dihydroxyacetophenacylidene-2,5-dichloroaniline, *N*-4-methylphenacylideneanthranilic acid and *N*-4-methylphenacylidene-*o*-aminophenol were prepared and characterised as reported earlier⁶⁻⁸.

Platinum chloride (A.R.) was dissolved in minimum quantity of hot concentrated HCl and diluted with ethanol. The complexes of Pt^{II} were isolated by refluxing a stoichiometric mixture of metal chloride and each ligand in ethanol solution on water bath for 4.5-5.0 h. On refrigeration for few days the reaction mixture yielded yellow coloured crystals of the complexes which were washed with water, ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum (65-75%), decomposition temperatures 210-254°.

The complexes were analysed for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen on Thomas CH Analyser-35 and Coleman N-Analyser-29, and Pt was estimated gravimetrically as DMG or ammonium chloroplatinate complexes. Magnetic and electronic and infrared spectral studies were made as reported earlier⁹, pmr spectra in $CDCl_3$ were recorded on Varian T-60 instrument using TMS as internal

standard. The ligand-metal ratio was determined by pH-metric titrations on Philips PP 9040 pH-meter and showed 1 : 1 (M : L) complexation. Conductance measurements were carried out using a Beckman RC-18A conductivity bridge. The colour and elemental analysis data of the complexes are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Pt^{II} CHELATES OF SCHIFF BASES

Sl. no.	Complexes	Colour	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)		
			N	Cl	Pt
1.	$H^+[Pt(C_{15}H_{11}NO_4)Cl]^-$	Yellow	2.53 (2.79)	6.80 (7.09)	38.71 (38.96)
2.	$[Pt(C_{14}H_{10}NO_2Cl_2)Cl]$	Bright yellow	2.45 (2.66)	18.04 (18.36)	36.85 (37.10)
3.	$[Pt(C_{16}H_{12}NO_3)Cl]$	Yellow	2.61 (2.84)	6.90 (7.15)	41.28 (41.49)
4.	$[Pt(C_{16}H_{12}NO_2)Cl]$	Dirty yellow	2.81 (3.00)	7.42 (7.60)	39.46 (39.69)

*Satisfactory C and H analyses found for all complexes.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data reveal 1 : 1 (M : L) stoichiometry for all the complexes. The molar conductance of the complexes ($10^{-3}M$ solutions) were measured in DMF medium. Δ_m values for the complexes 2, 3 and 4 in the range 0.56-0.94 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ indicate non-electrolytic nature of the compounds, the remaining complex 1 showed Δ_m value 98.5 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ indicating its uni-unielectrolytic nature. The complexes are diamagnetic as expected.

The electronic spectra Pt^{II} complexes showed bands in the regions 17000-18700, 20000-21600, 24500-25500, 28000-28800, 30600-31000 and 32500-33000 cm^{-1} . The first three bands are assigned to the transitions ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{A}_{2g}$, ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$ and ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{E}_g$ in order of increasing energy suggesting square planar environment around metal atom^{10,11}. The higher energy bands in the regions 28000-28800 and 30600-31000 cm^{-1} may be attributed to ligand and metal charge transfer transitions¹² or square planar¹³ ($\sim 30000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{A}_{2g}$). The band occurring at 32650 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) transitions of the ligands. The values of various single electron parameters Δ_1 , Δ_2 and Δ_3 have been calculated and their values are comparable to those observed for other platinum complexes involving similar donor atoms¹⁴. The values are (Δ_1) 21300, 21500, 21700 and 21200, (Δ_2) 5700, 5900, 6000, 5800, and (Δ_3) 3500, 3150, 3000 and 3600 cm^{-1} , respectively for platinum 1 to 4 complexes.

Ir and pmr spectral studies: In the ir spectra of Pt^{II} complexes with all four ligands the stretching frequencies of azomethine $-(\text{CH}_3)-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ or $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ (ligands ~ 1600 and in the complexes band around 1495-1550 cm^{-1}) are lowered, showing thereby complex formation through these groups^{15,16}. Anthranilic acid ligands (H_3DAPA and HMPAA) exhibit bands¹⁷ at $\sim 2700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to OH of carboxylic group, however, the bands disappeared in the complexes due to deprotonation. Phenolate ligands (H_3DAPA , H_2DAPDA and HMPAP) show stretching frequency due to OH at $\sim 3450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, however, these frequencies are also shifted to the region 3350-3400 cm^{-1} because of complexation with Pt^{II} . This view is further supported by the appearance of bands corresponding to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ (490-520) and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$ (450-470 cm^{-1}) bands. In all the complexes, metal-halogen bonds are also present as indicated by the appearance of bands $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{Cl}}$ (350-375 cm^{-1})¹⁸. The bands around $\sim 3280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (in the complexes of H_3DAPA and H_2DAPDA) are assigned to the

second hydroxyl group which does not enter into the reaction. The acyl ligands (HMPAA and HMPAP) show bands at $\sim 1700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$, however, these stretching frequencies were found to disappear indicating complex formation through this group.

The mode of bonding discussed above gets further support by the pmr spectral data (chemical shift in δ values down field from TMS internal reference) of the ligands, H_3DAPA , H_2DAPDA , HMPAA and HMPAP and its corresponding 1:1 platinum complexes.

The azomethine methyl protons $[-(\text{CH}_3)-\text{C}=\text{N}-]$ appear at $\delta 2.9$ in the ligands H_3DAPA and H_2DAPDA and at 3.13 and 3.19 in their platinum complexes. A comparison of the azomethine proton $(-\text{CH}=\text{N}-)$ signal $\delta 8.50$ in the ligands HMPAA and HMPAP with that of the resulting metal complexes ($\delta 8.68$ and 8.69), respectively shows down field shift and this may be due to the deshielding caused by coordination through the azomethine group to platinum.

The peak at $\delta 9.40$ due to the phenolic proton of the ligands H_3DAPA , H_2DAPDA and HMPAP disappears in the complex 4 indicating chelating nature of the ligands. However, in complexes 1 and 2 this peak is observed indicating that one of the phenolic OH of the ligand moiety remains uncoordinated. The peak at $\delta 12.00$ due to the carboxylic group proton of the ligands H_3DAPA and HMPAA disappears in the complexes 1 and 3 due to coordination through the carboxylic group to metal. A number of signals between $\delta 6.70$ to 7.85 appear due to aromatic protons in all compounds in addition to a singlet ($\delta 1.96$) due to a methyl group in the ligands HMPAA and HMPAP and their complexes. The *ortho* protons in the ligands HMPAA and HMPAP are shifted further down field because of the additional deshielding effect of carbonyl group¹⁹ and coordination through this group.

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References

1. H. E. GRAY and C. J. BALLHANSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
2. F. A. COTTON and C. B. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 369.
3. W. R. MASON and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 55 ; *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 5721.
4. P. SINGH, B. P. SINGH, V. SINGH and R. L. GOEL, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1977, **92**, 143.
5. G. P. POKHARIYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 182 ; *Acta Cincia Indica C*, 1980, **6**, 25.
6. P. SINGH and G. P. POKHARIYAL, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1977, **94**, 11.
7. V. K. AGARWAL, Ph. D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1980.
8. G. P. POKHARIYAL, Ph. D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1979.
9. G. P. POKHARIYAL and S. K. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **56**, 1199.
10. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
11. C. K. JORGENSEN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 1571.
12. K. NAG and D. S. JOARDAR, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1974, **14**, 133.
13. M. P. TEOTIA, J. N. GURTU and V. B. RANA, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 520.
14. M. P. TEOTIA, D. K. RASTOGI and W. U. MALIK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 343.
15. V. B. RANA, Ph. D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1975.
16. J. CSASZAR and L. KISS, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1973, **78**, 17.
17. D. D. OZHA, K. N. KAUL and S. MEHTA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1974, **43**, 344.
18. N. SONODA and T. TANAKA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **12**, 261.
19. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 2nd. ed., 1967, P. 117.